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A NOVEL APPROACH FOR AIR QUALITY TREND STUDIES AND ITS APPLICATION TO EUROPEAN URBAN ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract: Studying future climatic change effects on atmospheric processes and air quality one should consider the inherent uncertainties in trying to mathematically describe the associated phenomena. When quantifying such processes is more reliable to talk about trends rather than absolute values. Within the objectives of the present study is to provide high space and time resolution concentrations trends for the period 2001-2050, following the moderate Representative Concentration Pathway - RCP4.5, on major air pollutants (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, O₃) in Europe, focusing on nine (9) cities i.e. Thessaloniki, Athens, Madrid, Stuttgart, Ljubljana, Brno, Milan, Basel and Copenhagen/Roskilde. To achieve such an objective, a common approach in the past, has been to perform weather and air quality simulations for a complete year but only for a limited number of years. Such an approach has the inherent weakness that the results represent the selected year only and not the neighboring ones due to the high yearly weather variability. The present effort was to come up with a new approach that fulfills the study objectives by introducing proper trend indicators and targeted weather and air quality simulations. Thus, a novel approach based on weather clustering is inaugurated to study climate change effect on air quality levels. The adopted clustering technique has been applied in daily weather data of 50-year period (2001-2050). The clustering exercise results are examined over 5-year periods, instead of one (1) year. The detailed weather data were derived from the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) provided from the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) index nodes. The Regional Climate Model (RCM) INERIS-WRF331F was selected, using the EUR 11 (about 10 km resolution) horizontal domain projection. The detailed atmospheric modeling was performed using WRF-Chem and it has been restricted to cluster representative days in each of the above mentioned 5-years period. The study has provided interesting results on concentrations and heat wave trends revealing among others the correlation between weather patterns with higher heat wave events and elevated O₃ concentrations strengthening the hypothesis that the greenhouse effect leads to intensification of the atmospheric photochemical activity.

Key words: *Climate Change, weather clustering, urban air quality.*

INTRODUCTION

To study future climatic change effects on certain subjects such as atmospheric processes and air quality one should consider the inherent uncertainties in trying to mathematically describe the associated phenomena and quantify the relevant input due mainly to lack of knowledge and missing accurate enough input data. For answers that require high temporal and spatial refinements one should consider also the issue of computational capacity. Consideration should be given also to the additional difficulty due to high temporal variability of the defining parameters not only on the level of hour and day but also on the level of the year and even beyond.

The objective of the present study is to provide high space and time resolution ground concentrations reflecting climatic trends for the period 2001-2050, of major air pollutants (PM, NO₂, O₃) in Europe, focusing on the nine (9) cities i.e. Thessaloniki, Athens, Madrid, Stuttgart, Ljubljana, Brno, Milan, Basel and Copenhagen/Roskilde and to assess the effect of climate and emissions changes over time on the air concentration levels of the abovementioned pollutants. The whole effort falls within the frame of European ICARUS Project (<https://icarus2020.eu/>).

To achieve such an objective and given the today computational capacity limitations, the common approach in the past has been to perform weather and air quality simulations for a complete year but only for a limited number of years. Such an approach has the inherent weakness that the results represent the selected year only and not even the neighboring ones due to the inherent high yearly variability.

Taking into consideration all the above-mentioned complexities, the effort in the present study was to come up with a new and smart approach that fulfills the project objective by introducing proper trend indicators and targeted weather and air quality simulations.

METHODOLOGY

A novel approach based on weather clustering is inaugurated to study climate change effect on air quality levels. The approach mainly consists of classifying daily weather data of 50-year period (from 2001 to 2050) into an appropriate number of clusters using Principal Components Analysis and k-means Cluster analysis (Austin et al., 2014). Following the climatic scenario RCP4.5 (van Vuuren et al., 2011) and using the set of the CORDEX (<http://cordex.org>) data (spatial resolution ~10km) produced by INERIS-WRF331F model for the period 2001-2050, specific weather clusters for each one of the nine cities focusing on a 50km x 50km area around the city centre. To cope with the abovementioned high temporal weather variability, the clustering exercise results are examined over 5-year periods, i.e. 2001-2005 up to 2046-2050, instead of one year.

The cluster interpretation methodology includes (a) Cluster characterization with respect to weather parameters, (b) Cluster frequency of occurrence along the 50-year period as a climatic change indicator, (c) Frequency of occurrence of heat waves (Guerreiro, 2018) as an additional climatic change indicator and (d) Clusters associated with elevated observed concentrations in the city area for the priority air pollutants.

The detailed atmospheric modeling has been restricted to cluster representative days in each of the above mentioned 5-years period. It is noticed that a representative day per cluster per 5-year period is identified. The WRF-Chem model (<https://ruc.noaa.gov/wrf/wrf-chem/>) has been utilised for this purpose, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The atmospheric modelling layout

For the air quality modelling the University of Stuttgart (USTUTT) High Resolution (1km x1km) Emission Inventory Data for the years 2015, 2020 and 2030 was used. This inventory has been produced within ICARUS project.

The Pollutant Representative concentration (CR) as a new air quality climatic change indicator has been introduced as follows in equation (1):

$$CR(\Delta\tau) = \sum_{n=1}^N f_n(\Delta\tau) \cdot CRD_n(\Delta\tau) \quad (1)$$

Where, N is the total number of Clusters, $f_n(\Delta\tau)$ is the frequency of occurrence of cluster n during the specific time period $\Delta\tau$ (5years), $CRD_n(\Delta\tau)$ is the concentration under study corresponding to the representative day of the cluster n during the specific time period $\Delta\tau$ (5years).

RESULTS AND SUMMARY

The Athens Example

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. (a) O₃ Concentrations per cluster (b) Heat Waves per cluster (c) O₃ Daily max concentrations per 5-year period (d) Cluster 4 frequency of occurrence per 5-year period

The Stuttgart Example

Figure 3. (a) NO₂ hourly max concentrations per 5-year period (b) O₃ hourly max concentrations per 5-year period (c) PM_{2.5} daily max concentrations per 5-year period

The results obtained for the nine cities have led to following key findings:

1. The present study reinforces the view that the greenhouse effect is likely to be 'felt' even under a moderate climatic scenario such as RCP4.5. For the cities of Stuttgart, Ljubljana, Brno, Milan, Basel and Copenhagen/Roskilde the results indicate that adverse effects at least in terms of heat wave event frequency for this specific scenario, seem to reach maxima in the early 40s. For the cities of the south (Athens, Thessaloniki, Madrid) the maxima shift late 40s and probably beyond.
2. The elevated numbers of heat waves are associated with specific weather clusters;
3. There is a correlation between weather patterns with higher heat wave events and weather patterns with elevated O₃ concentrations. This is an indication that the greenhouse effect seems to lead to elevated O₃ concentrations likely due to the intensified atmospheric photochemical activity.
4. With respect to cluster frequency trend over the 50-year period changes are observed. More specifically:
 - For all cities, the clusters associated with elevated heat wave events and O₃ concentrations show an increase.
 - The clusters associated with elevated PM show an increase only in Stuttgart and Madrid.

- The clusters with elevated NO₂ concentrations show an increase in the five cities: Stuttgart, Brno, Basel, Madrid and Ljubljana.
5. Regarding the Air Quality trends:
- NO₂ show decreasing trends since early 20s from most of the cities. The exception is for Thessaloniki, Milan and Madrid where there are no visible trends for this period.
 - O₃ concentration levels do not show visible trends in all cities except Athens and Basel. In Athens there is decrease until 20s and an increasing trend afterwards and in Basel there is a decreasing trend after 20s.
 - PM concentration levels show decreasing trends since early 20s for the cities Stuttgart, Basel, Roskilde, Copenhagen and Ljubljana. The exception is for Brno, Athens, Milan, Madrid and Thessaloniki where there are no clearly visible trends. In the city of Thessaloniki, it's seems to be a decrease in period 2020-2030. In general terms PM level trends seem to have an analogous behavior with NO₂ level trends.

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